

Garden Cress (*Lepidium sativum* L.) Seeds - An Nutritional Composition of Garden Cress Seeds : A Review

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Abstract

Lepidium sativum, a member of the Brassicaceae family, is commonly referred to as garden cress seed among other common names. Around the world, garden cress seeds are extensively grown as an oilseed crop, culinary ingredient, and traditional medicine. Iron, omega-3 fatty acids, dietary fiber, proteins, and other vital elements and phytochemicals are all abundant in its seeds. It is quite nutrient-dense because it has 30.7g of carbohydrates, 24.2g of protein, and 23.2g of lipids per 100g. Antibacterial, antifungal, antiasthmatic, diuretic, anti-anemic, anti-diabetic, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, hepatoprotective, and chemoprotective are only a few of the pharmacological qualities of garden cress seeds. The current review addresses garden cress seeds' nutritional, phytochemical, antimicrobial, toxicological, and therapeutic potential. It emphasizes coagulant, analgesic, fracture healing, laxative, hypocholesterolemic, and anti-diabetic properties.

Keywords

Lepidium Sativum, Phytochemicals, Antimicrobial Activities, Medicinal Properties.

Introduction

Lepidium sativum also known as Garden cress (GC) seeds belong to Brassicaceae family which is also known as mustard family., *Lepidium sativum* is an annual, herbaceous edible plant that is botanically related to mustard and watercress. Gc plant is native to Egypt and South west Asia. It is cultivated in India (KM Nadkarni and AK Nadkarni.1954) North America and parts of Europe (F Nuez and JE Hernandez Bermejo). In some regions, Gc is known as garden pepper grass, pepper cress, pepperwort or poor man's pepper (Amin,2005; Avachat & Dhamne 2002). It is extensively cultivated for various purposes such as cooking, traditional medicines and as an oilseed crop all over the world. It does not require a lot of agricultural resources as it is suitable to be cultivated in any type of climate and it has an ability to tolerate slightly acidic soil and can be grown like white mustard (Lahiri and Rani., 2020). It can grow well in semiarid regions, in low fertility soils and in temperate climate where the average rainfall varies from 300-2000mm. According to scientific research, garden cress seeds have 80–85% endosperm, 12–17% seed coat and 2–3% embryo. The garden cress features sessile leaves, small white flowers, and obovate or broad pods, all of which are edible. The parts of the plant which are used are the roots, leaves and seeds. The seeds of *L. sativum* are bitter and find applications in a wide range of biological functions and diseases such as leprosy, skin diseases and as a diuretic. The roots are bitter and acrid and have been used in treating secondary syphilis and tenesmus. The leaves of *Lepidium sativum* possess number of health benefits and have a tangy taste because of which they are employed in preparation of salads and are antibacterial and useful in treating scurvy and hepatopathy. (Amin G.H, et al, 2005).

Objective of study

1. To analyse the Nutritional composition of Garden seeds.
2. To analyse the Phytochemical compounds present in Garden Cress Seeds.
3. To observe health benefits of garden cress seed.

Review of Literature

Bikranjitsingh et al.,(2022) conducted a review study titled "Lepidium sativum: Its nutritional composition and therapeutic properties" reported that garden seed has 30.7g of carbohydrates, 24.2g of protein, and 23.2g of fats, it is quite nutrient-dense. It has properties of Antibacterial, antifungal, anti asthmatic, diuretic, anti-anaemic, anti-diabetic, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, hepatoprotective, and other pharmacological qualities are all present in garden cress seeds. It has numerous health advantages, including preventing anemia, regulating the menstrual cycle, preventing cancer, and boosting the production of breast milk. Despite its numerous positive qualities, it may be dangerous because of its teratogenicity effect, which can result in toxicity or allergies if

taken in excess. It further emphasized that it is commercially available in the market and utilized in the creation of a variety of culinary products with added value. These value-added food items, which aim to enhance people's general health, include noodles, iron-rich cookies, fortified health drinks, Fortified Dahi-wala bread and muffins, nutrient-rich cutlets, and instant UPMA mix.

Tabussam Tufail et al., (2024) conducted a review titled "Garden cress seeds: a review on nutritional composition, therapeutic potential, and industrial utilization" concluded that *Lepidium sativum* (Garden Cress) is a nutritionally rich and pharmacologically versatile plant, containing essential proteins, fatty acids, minerals, vitamins, and diverse bioactive compounds that contribute to its wide range of therapeutic properties. Despite its proven antioxidant, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and functional health benefits, it remains one of the most underutilized crops globally. Greater scientific exploration and industrial utilization of its phytochemical and nutritional potential could pave the way for novel applications in food, pharmaceuticals, and nutraceuticals

Main Text

The taxonomic classification [George et al. 1959]

Kingdom (Plantae), Division (Magnoliophyta), Class (Magnoliopsida), Order (Brassicales)
Family : Brassicaceae (Genus) of *Lepidium sativum*

Vernacular names of Garden cress Plant in India : (Snehal Doke and Manisha Guha)
Candriki (Assamese) ; Chand Shura (Sanskrit); Aadal (Telugu); Chandasura (Oriya); Chansur (Hindi); Common Cress (English); Halim (Urdu / Bengali); Holan (Punjabi); Haliv (Marathi); Alian (Kashmiri); Allibija (Kannada); Allivirai (Tamil); Asali (Malayalam); Aseliyo (Gujrati).

Nutritional Composition

It is well known that garden cress seeds are a nutrient-dense food that offers a wide range of vital macronutrients, vitamins, and minerals. Their potential as a beneficial dietary component is highlighted by their thorough nutritional profile.

Proximate nutritional composition of Garden cress seeds

Garden cress is considered a superfood due to its highly nutritious profile. It has a protein content of 21–25%, which is essential for muscle growth and tissue repair. Fat (23–25%) and carbohydrates (30–34%) make the seeds a good source of energy for those who are undernourished (Zia-UI-Haq et al., 2011).

Macronutrients availability of Garden cress seed

It provides a good amount of calories (454 kcal/100g) (Gopalan et al., 2004), Protein (24.2), fat (23.2), carbohydrate (30.7), fiber (11.9), ash (7.1), and moisture (2.9) were found in garden cress seeds (Zia-UI-Haq et al., 2011). Ash content indicates the seeds are an appreciable source of minerals. The low moisture content is an index of stability, quality and increased shelf life of seeds. Higher protein and lipids indicate that these seeds have high food energy (Vincenzo et al. 2012). There are a number of factors that affect its proximate composition, including plant species, seed variation, agronomic techniques, climatic and geographical conditions, and the stage at which seeds are gathered. Fruit and seed nutritional quality can be assessed using this factor, and further research is encouraged on components that are more intriguing (Zia-UI-Haq et al., 2011). Low moisture content seeds are more stable, more nutritious, and have a longer shelf life (Alsadee & Agbashee, 2021; Bathish et al., 2021).

Micronutrients

The major minerals present in garden seed are prominent amount of potassium (1635.62 mg/100g), and phosphorus (723 mg/100g), whereas the manganese content is low. It is also a good source of calcium (480.72 mg/100g), magnesium (631.06 mg/100g) and iron (100 mg/100g) (Gopalan et al. 2011), which will be useful to make post pregnancy diet in India (Pattnaik, 2003). It also corrects contraction of muscle for healthy limbs and heart motions. As they are in reduced amount of sodium (36.25 mg/100g), so they can be utilized as an ingredient of health food. Garden cress seeds can be used as diet for athletes who are involved in hard exercise and for suffering from high blood pressure disorder (Luft FC 1987).

Garden cress (*Lepidium sativum*, family - Cruciferae) (Dhiman, 2006) has been considered as an important nutritional and medicinal plant in India due to its health promoting properties (Mahasni and Al-Reemi, 2013; Mohite et al., 2012; Doke and Guha, 2014) and its seed contains most remarkable proportion for Vitamin B complex, that is higher in amount of (Thiamine, 0.59 mg/100g; riboflavin, 0.61 mg/100g; Niacin, 14.3 mg/100g) (Gopalan et al., 2011).

Garden cress is considered as a good source of ascorbic acid, and this property boosts its effectiveness against infection and diseases. Sat et al. (2013) reported that ascorbic acid (Vitamin C) content in *L. sativum* leaves ranges from 54 to 74 mg/100 g FW. Another study was also done to probe the ascorbic acid content in the stem, leaves, whole plant, and seeds of *L. sativum* and found 11.74 mg, 7.4 mg, 12.5 mg, and 9.68 mg, respectively (Malar et al., 2014).

Garden The garden cress seeds'(GCS) oil is a rich source of tocopherol (Vitamin E) which acts as a natural antioxidant. The total amount of tocopherol in GCS oil is about (139.73±0.91mg/100g) in which (17.19±0.52 mg/100g) consists of α -tocopherol and (111.55±0.37mg/100g) consists of β - tocopherol and γ - tocopherol (Zia-UI-Haq et al.,2012) .

Amino acids

The seed protein of garden cress is of high quality and contains necessary amino acids such as lysine (6.26 g) and phenylalanine (5.65 g). Methionine (0.97 g) is a limiting amino acid in the seeds (Gopalan *et al.*, 1971).e (0.97 g) is a limiting amino acid in the seeds (Gopalan *et al.*, 1971). Garden cress seeds contain all the essential amino acids, except for tryptophan and the S-containing amino acids methionine and cysteine, which are only present in trace amounts.garden cress seeds are rich in two primary, non-essential amino acids: glutamic acid and aspartic acid. The oilseed analysis showed that aspartic acid (9.76 ± 0.03%) and glutamic acid (19.33 ± 0.19%) were the most abundant amino acids in garden cress seeds (AbdelAty, Bassuiny, et al., 2019; Abdel-Aty, Salama, *et al.*, 2019; Sedeeq *et al.*, 2021).

Fatty acids

Essential fatty acids (linoleic acids and arachidic acids) of these seeds are used as memory boosters (Jagdale *et al.*, 2021). Oil withdrawn from garden cress seeds is extremely beneficial as its polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) value is 46.8% and monounsaturated fatty acids (MUFA) value is 37.6% thereby making the seeds a great source of fatty acids for our body which helps in increasing our metabolism and reducing the risk of diseases such as cardio vascular diseases, cancer, obesity, asthma and arthritis (Maheswaraiyah *et al.*, 2018). These seeds also contain vitamin A and vitamin E which helps in the protection of cells from the damage and protects the Garden Cress seeds oil from oxidation and rancidity (Lahiri and Rani., 2020). The total essential amino acid percentage is 47.08%, with 6.26 ± 0.39% lysine and 0.97 ± 0.02% methionine. Tryptophan and cysteine were not determined. Essential amino acid score was 28.53% with methionine as the most limiting amino acid. Lysine helps to maintain proper nitrogen balance. The body uses methionine to derive the brain food, choline. It also aids in digestion, as well as serving as a fat burner. It can interact with other substances to detoxify harmful agents and is essential for the production of cysteine and taurine (Zia-UI-Haq *et al.*, 2012).

Phytochemicals

Garden cress is considered as a multifarious functional and medicinal plant as it possesses high levels of various phytochemicals such as alkaloids, terpenes, glucosinolates, and saturated and essential fatty acids in the seeds, leaves, seed oil, and roots. Some other important bioactive compounds in garden cress are gallic acid, protocatechuic acid, coumaric acid, caffeic acid, kaempferol glucuronide, and many others. The methanolic extract of defatted seeds has yielded phenolic components such as sinapic acid and sinapin (Oe & Gmelin, 1952). Flavonoids are the most prevalent and abundant class of plant polyphenols that can be obtained from a diet high in plants (Gupta & Morya, 2022). Subclasses of flavonoids (C6–C3–C6) may be divided into flavones, flavanones, flavanols, isoflavones, flavanols, chalcones, and anthocyanins, and they are usually found conjugated to sugars in the form of O-glycosides or C-glycosides, which are the most prevalent (Gupta & Morya, 2022). The seeds of *Lepidium sativum* have recently yielded two novel acylated kaempferol and quercetin chemicals, which have just been discovered. The total phenolic and flavonoid contents and antioxidant activity increased several times during the germination of garden cress seeds (Xiao et al., 2014).

Antioxidants

Highly reactive free radicals and oxygen species are present in biological systems from a wide variety of sources. These free radicals may oxidize nucleic acids, proteins, lipids or DNA and can initiate degenerative diseases. Antioxidant has ability to trap these free radicals. Antioxidant compounds like phenolic acids, polyphenols and flavonoids scavenge free radicals such as peroxide, hydro peroxide or lipid peroxy and thus inhibit the oxidative mechanisms that lead to degenerative diseases.

(R Indumathy and A Aruna) (2013) evaluated the free radical scavenging activity of total phenolic and flavonoid compounds extracted from Gc seeds. The methanolic extract was found to contain a noticeable amount of total phenols (8.651mgGAE/gm) and flavonoids (4.023 mg CAE/gm). Methanolic extract of Gc seeds showed maximum antioxidant activity by inhibiting DPPH and hydroxyl radical, super oxide anion scavenging, nitric oxide and hydrogen peroxide scavenging activities than the reference standards studied.

Antinutritional Factor

Antinutritional compounds are those compounds that interfere with the absorption of nutrients in the body and metabolic processes and reduce the absorption of macro- and

micronutrients (Singh *et al.*, 2018). Garden cress seeds have a few anti-nutritional compounds such as phytin phosphorus, oxalates, tannins, protease inhibitors, saponins, phytic acid, lectins, and amylase inhibitors. Among these compounds, phytin phosphorus and oxalates are mainly present in raw garden cress seeds (Azene *et al.*, 2022). It was observed that there was reduction in the value of phytin phosphorus and oxalates when processing methods were applied on them. Most of the depletion in the level of phytin by boiling which was more than other two methods of processing methods (soaking and roasting). About 9.65% decline in the value of total phytin phosphorus after boiling and the resultant value was 404.03mg/100g. The reduction was seen in the level of phytin phosphorus after soaking and roasting and the outcome values were 431.5 and 440.03mg/100g with 3.51 and 0.46% drop respectively (Gopalan *et al.*, 2011; Jain *et al.*, 2016). It was noticed that the oxalates' value in the raw seeds was about 134mg/100g. While by boiling, about 14.13% depletion in the oxalates level and the final value was observed 115.06mg/100g which is noticeable decrease, whereas the least reduction (4.98%) was computed by roasting which was about 127.33 mg/100g. Furthermore, by applying the soaking method, 120.73mg/100g was the outcome value with 9.90% decrease from the initial value (Gopalan *et al.*, 2011; Jain *et al.*, 2016) .

Antibacterial Activity

In a study on *Lepidium sativum* seeds was to estimate the possible antibacterial activity of several seed extracts (Petroleum ether, methanolic and water) at concentrations of (2.5, 5 and 10%) against six pathogenic bacteria (*Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Proteus vulgaris*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and one fungus *Candida albicans*), The antimicrobial activity of plant seeds extracts were compared with that of Gentamicin or Ketoconazole, as reference antibiotics (Sharma *et al.*, 2011). The presence of benzyl isothiocyanate, flavonoids, tannins, Triterpenes, alkaloids, sterols, glucosinolates confirmed the antimicrobial effect. Tannins in particular act by inhibition of protein synthesis by forming irreversible complex with prolina rich proteins. Few example of garden seed - based food products are :- Noodle (Hanan *et al.*, (2019) ,Instant mix ; Yadav, Singh ,Sharma, Bhatt and Govila (2018), Health drinks (Lahiri and Rani (2020) Cookies (Yadav, Singh, Sharma, Bhatt and Govila(2018), Pinni(Bansal,2013), Panjiri (Nagi and Mann, 2003), Laddu, Burfi, Chikki, Biscuits, Spread Muffin, Bar.10%)

Conclusion

The seeds of the garden cress plant (*Lepidium sativum*) are a nutrient-dense and useful plant part with enormous potential for use in food and medicine. Protein, dietary fiber, essential fatty acids, vitamins A, C, E, and B-complex, and minerals including calcium, magnesium, potassium, and iron are all abundant in these seeds. Their strong antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant properties are attributed to the presence of bioactive substances such as alkaloids, phenolic acids, flavonoids, and glucosinolates. Their many health benefits, including as their anti-diabetic, antihypertensive, hypocholesterolemic, fracture-healing, and galactagogue qualities, have been scientifically shown. This makes them particularly advantageous for nursing mothers and those who are malnourished. The bioavailability of nutrients is improved by proper processing techniques like boiling and soaking, which successfully lower the amounts of certain antinutritional substances like phytates and oxalates. Furthermore, the seeds are a sustainable crop choice due to their high yield, low resource requirements, and capacity to adapt to a variety of agroclimatic situations. Their addition to a variety of food items, including cookies, health drinks, traditional sweets, and fortified mixes, not only increases their nutritional content but also fosters the creation of functional foods. To sum up, garden cress seeds are a promising component of functional foods and nutraceuticals. These seeds have the potential to greatly improve public health and fight lifestyle-related illnesses in a sustainable and culturally acceptable way with greater consumer awareness, additional study, and product innovation.

References

1. Abdel-Aty, A. M., Bassuiny, R. I., Barakat, A. Z., & Mohamed, S. A. (2019). *Upgrading the phenolic content, antioxidant and antimicrobial activities of garden cress seeds using solid-state fermentation by Trichoderma reesei*. *Journal of Applied Microbiology*, 127(5), 1454– 1467. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jam.14394>
2. Abdel-Aty, A. M., Salama, W. H., Fahmy, A. S., & Mohamed, S. A. (2019). *Impact of germination on antioxidant capacity of garden cress: New calculation for determination of total antioxidant activity*. *Scientia Horticulturae*, 246, 155–160. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scienta.2018.10.062>
3. Amin G.H.,2005.*Medicinal plant of iran (in Persian language)*(1st ed). Tehran:Tehran Uuniversity Publication.106.
4. Alsadee, A., & Agbashee, S. (2021). *Hepato-nephroprotective role of Lepidium sativum against oxidative stress induced by dexamethasone in rats*. *Indian Journal of Forensic Medicine and Toxicology*, 15(1), 2643–2653. Al-Jasass, F.M. and Al-Jasser, M.S. (2012). *Chemical composition and fatty acid content of some spices and herbs under Saudi Arabia conditions*. *The Scientific World Journal*.doi: 10.1100/2012/859892

5. Azene, M., Habte, K., & Tkuwab, H. (2022). Nutritional, health benefits and toxicity of underutilized garden cress seeds and its functional food products: A review. *Food Production, Processing and Nutrition*, 4(1), 1–13.
6. Bathish, Y., El Kilani, N., Dawaba, A., & Farid, Z. (2021). Effect of *Lepidium sativum* gel as an adjunct to non-surgical treatment in Management of Periodontitis Patients Stage (II, III) and grade (A, B). *Al-Azhar*
7. Bikramjit Singh et al.(2022), *Lepidium sativum: Its nutritional composition and therapeutic properties*,*The Pharma Innovation Journal* 2022; 11(7): 15-25,
8. Dental Journal for Girls, 8(2-C), 285–292. Dhiman,A.K.(2006).Ayurvedic drug plant. Daya Publishing House,delhi ,pp 97-99.
9. Doke, S. and Guha, M. (2014). Garden cress (*Lepidium sativum* L.) seed- an important medicinal source: a review *J. Nat. Prod. Plant Resour.* 4(1): 69-80.
10. Domestic Iranian seeds, Research project No.1475, Unpublished report, Ferdowsi University of Mashhad, Iran.
11. Eddouks M, Maghrani M, Lemhadri A, Ouahidi ML, Jouad H. Ethno pharmacological survey of medicinal plants used for the treatment of diabetes mellitus, hypertension and cardiac diseases in the south-east region of Morocco (Tafilaleet). *Journal of ethno pharmacology.* 2002 Oct 1;82(2-3):97-103.
12. F Nuez, JE Hernandez Bermejo. *Plant Production and Protection Series No. 26*, Rome, Italy: FAO, 1994, 303– 332.
13. Garden Cress Seeds (*Lepidium sativum* L.) as Natural Source of Protein and Dietary Fiber in Noodles. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Research & Allied Sciences.* 2019 Jul 1, 8(3)
14. Gopalan, C., Sastri, B.V.R., Balasubramanian, S.C., Rao, B.S.N., Deosthale, Y.G. and Pant, K.C. (2011). Nutritive Value of Indian Foods. National Institute of Nutrition, Indian Council of Medical Research, Hyderabad, India.
15. Gupta, N., & Morya, S. (2022). Bioactive and pharmacological characterization of *Chenopodium quinoa*, *Sorghum bicolor* and *Linum usitassimum*: A review. *Journal of Applied and Natural Science*, 14(3), 1067–1084.
16. Hanan MA, Nahla SZ, Abdelaleem MA. Utilization of Garden Cress Seeds (*Lepidium sativum* L.) as Natural Source of Protein and Dietary Fiber in Noodles. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Research & Allied Sciences.* 2019 Jul 1, 8(3).
17. HM Lawrence George, United Sates of America: An introduction of the plant Taxonomy, 1959 taxanomy .
18. Jain T, Grover K, Grewal IS. Development and sensory evaluation of ready to eat supplementary food using garden cress (*Lepidium sativum*) seeds. *Journal of Applied and Natural Science.* 2016 Sep 1;8(3):1501-6
19. Khan N, Adhami VM, Mukhtar H. Apoptosis by dietary agents for prevention and treatment of cancer. *Biochemical pharmacology.* 2008 Dec 1;76(11):1333-9.
20. KM Nadkarni, AK Nadkarni.- , India, 1954, 736–737. Garden cress (*Lepidium sativum* L.) Seed - An Important Medicinal Source: A Review 1 Snehal Doke and 2Manisha Guha.
21. Lahiri B, Rani R. Garden Cress Seeds: chemistry, medicinal properties, application in dairy and food industry: A Review. *Emergent Life Sciences Research.* 2020 Dec;6:1-4.
22. Malar, J., Chairman, K., Singh, A. R., Vanmathi, J. S., Balasubramanian, A., & Vasanthi, K. (2014). Antioxidative activity of different parts of the plant *Lepidium sativum* Linn. *Biotechnology Reports*, 3, 95–98.
23. Mahassni,S.H. and Al- Reemi,R.M(2013).Apoptosis and necrosis of human breast cancer by an aqueous extract of garden cress(*lipidium sativum* L.) seeds *Saudi J. Biol.Sci.*20:131-139
24. Mali RG, Mahajan SG, Mehta AA. Studies on bronchodilatory effect of *Lepidium sativum* against allergen induced bronchospasm in guinea pigs. *Pharmacognosy magazine.* 2008 Jul 1;4(15):189-92.
25. Oe, S., & Gmelin, R. (1952). Purification of glycoside from *Lepidium sativum* by chromatography on a cellulose powder column. *Arzneimittel-Forschung*, 2(12), 568–569.
26. Paranjape AN, Mehta AA. A study on clinical efficacy of *Lepidium sativum* seeds in treatment of bronchial asthma. *Iranian Journal of Pharmacology and Therapeutics.* 2006 Sep 10;5(1):55-0.
27. Pattnaik AK. Effect of herbal additives on lactating ruminants with or without subclinical mastitis (Doctoral dissertation, Thesis submitted to Orissa university of Agriculture and Technology, Bhubaneswar (Orissa) India).
28. physical properties of cress seed hydrocolloid using response surface methodology, PhD thesis, Ferdowsi University of Mashhad, Iran.
29. R Indumathy and A Aruna. *International Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2013, 5(4), 634-637.

30. Razavi S.M.A., Farhoosh R. and Bostan A., 2007. *Functional properties of hydrocolloid extract of some domestic Iranian seeds*, Research project No.1475, Unpublished report, Ferdowsi University of Mashhad, Iran.
31. Shama I. Y., Shayma A.M., Salih and Warda S.A., 2011. *In vitro Antimicrobial Assessment of Lepidium sativum L. Seeds Extracts*. *Asian Journal of Medical Sciences* 3(6), 261-266.
32. Singh, N., David, J., Thompkinson, D. K., Seelam, B. S., Rajput, H., & Morya, S. (2018). *Effect of roasting on functional and phytochemical constituents of finger millet (Eleusine coracana L.)*. *The Pharma Innovation Journal*, 7(4), 414–418.
33. Tabussam Tufail et al.,(2024),*Garden cress seeds: a review on nutritional composition, therapeutic potential, and industrial utilization*,*Food Sci Nutr*. 2024;12:3834 3848,
34. Watt J.M. and Brandwijk M.G., 1962. *Medicinal and Poisonous Plants of Southern and Eastern Africa*. 2nd Edn., Livingstone Ltd., Edinburgh.
35. Yadav A, Singh P, Sarma U, Bhatt G, Govila VK. *Nutritional and sensory attributes of cookies enriched with garden cress seeds*. *International Journal of Recent Scientific Research*. 2018 Oct;9(12):30146-9.
36. Xiao, J., Muzashvili, T. S., & Georgiev, M. I. (2014). *Advances in the biotechnological glycosylation of valuable flavonoids*. *Biotechnology Advances*, 32(6), 1145–1156. 2014.04.006
37. Zia-Ul-Haq M, Ahmad S, Calani L, Mazzeo T, Del Rio D, Pellegrini N, et al. *Compositional study and antioxidant potential of Ipomoea hederacea Jacq. and Lepidium sativum L. seeds*. *Molecules*. 2012 Sep;17(9):10306-21.
38. Zia-Ul-Haq, M., Čavar, S., Qayum, M., Imran, I., & de Feo, V. (2011). *Compositional studies: Antioxidant and antidiabetic activities of Capparis decidua (Forsk.) Edgew.* *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 12(12), 8846–8861.